

Table 1. Effect of K level on growth of hybrid rice Vu 35.^a Hunan, China.

K level (kg KCl/ha)	Tillering	Panicle initiation	Full heading	Maturity
	<i>Leaf area index</i>			
0	1.63	4.51	6.69	2.19
110	1.52	4.80	8.39**	3.64**
220	1.68	4.88	8.44**	4.34**
440	1.71	4.04	9.71**	4.10**
	<i>Net assimilation rate (A Dry matter mg/dm² per h)</i>			
0	10.5	12.3	8.1	7.0
110	1.9	13.3	9.0	9.3
220	8.6	9.5	11.0	8.9
440	10.9	13.2	11.4	8.9
	<i>Dry matter weight (g/plant)</i>			
0	2.73	8.13	19.47	27.17
110	2.73	8.27	26.10*	34.93*
220	2.96	8.30	21.97	33.73*
440	3.23	8.30	28.10*	35.27*

^aSignificance at the 5% (*) or 1% (**) levels by Duncan's multiple range test.

Table 2. Effect of K fertilization on yield and K absorption by hybrid rice and a conventional variety. Hunan, China.

Variety	K level (kg KCl/ha)	Yield (t/ha)	K absorbed (kg/ha)	K depleted (kg/t grain)	Grain increase (kg/kg K ₂ O)
Vu 35	0	8.5	107.8	12.72	
	100	8.7	147.9	16.92	4.8
	220	8.8	198.4	22.54	2.9
	440	9.2	250.9	27.42	3.0
Xiang 9	0	7.3	88.95	12.25	
	110	7.6	144.2	18.88	6.6
	220	7.4	190.3	25.68	1.3
	440	7.6	195.3	25.80	1.6

replications. Samples were taken at transplanting, tillering, panicle initiation, full heading, and maturity for soil, plant, and yield analyses.

Increased K increased K content in plant and absorbed K increased with increased K fertilizer at all stages for both varieties; however, Vu 35 was more sensitive to K supplied from panicle initiation to heading and needed more K. The leaf area index was significantly correlated with plant N content ($r = 0.91^*$) at early growth stages and with plant K content ($r = 0.94$) at late growth stages. Total photosynthetic area and net assimilation rate had increased significantly at heading and maturing stages, which led to 13-44% increase in dry matter production with K application (Table 1).

Grain yield of Vu 35 increased 3-8% with K level, but increase/kg K₂O applied declined (Table 2), resulting in lower K economic efficiency at higher K levels. Yield of Xiang 9 was significantly lower than that of Vu 35 and did not show obvious response to K fertilization. □

Test cross for restorer genes using three male sterile lines

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We tested crosses for restorer genes for the Thailand hybrid rice breeding program in 1982. Now we have 8 varieties and 10 elite breeding lines that are effective restorers for V20A. In 1985, we received male sterile lines IR46828A and IR46829A from IRRI and crossed 5 varieties and 10 elite breeding lines as male parents with 3 CMS lines — V20A, IR46828A, and IR46829A (which are the same WA type) — to identify their restorers (see table).

The F₁ hybrids were grown in the field. Spikelet fertility was evaluated visually for each plant. Varieties showing more than 80% spikelet fertility were classified as restorers. those

Restorers and maintainers^a for CMS lines V20A, IR46828A, and IR46829A in Thailand, 1986.

Variety	V20A	IR46828A	IR46829A
IR11418-19-2-3	PR	PR	PR
SPRLR75007-16-3-1	PR	PR	PR
SPRLR76037-2-164-1-1	M	M	M
CNTBR71011-59-2-2-2	PR	PR	PR
SPRLR76035-PSL-16-1-2	PR	PR	PR
SPRLR80187-21-1-1	PR	PR	PR
BKNLR77011-31-1-1-1-1	PR	PR	PR
SPRLR17034-PSL-17-1-1-1	R	PR	PR
SPRLR75055-352-2-1	R, PR	PR	PR
BKNLR77003-PSL-9-1-1	R	—	—
IR36	R	R	R
RD7	R	M	M
RD11	R	PR	PR
RD23	R	R	R
C4-63 (green)	R	M	M

^aR = restorer (>80% spikelet fertility), PR = partial restorer (5- 80% spikelet fertility), M = maintainer (<5% spikelet fertility), — = damaged seedlings.

showing 5-80% as partial restorers. and those with less than 5% as maintainers.

RD23 and IR36 were effective restorers for all 3 CMS lines. RD11, SPRLR77034-PSL-17-1-1-1, and SPRLR75055-352-2-1 were effective

restorers only for V20A. SPRLR76037-2-164-1-1 was an effective maintainer for all CMS lines. RD7 and C4-63 (green) were effective restorers for V20A, but maintainers for IR46828A and IR46829A. □